

ISic1062

I.Sicily inscription 1062

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Netum

Place of origin (modern)

near Noto

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [A]πτειλία Δόμ
2. [v]α Ίουλίω Πα[ύλ]
3. λω συμβίω γλ[υ]
4. κυτάτω μνία[ς]
5. χάριν (vac. undefined) καί
6. Παύλλη θυγατρ[ί]
7. ζησάση άμέμ
8. πτως έν Θ(εῶ) ἔτε
9. σιν ια ήμέραις λ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492689

EDR 140742; 150498

EDCS 39102217

PHI 140542

PHI 175746

PHI 333536

Bibliography

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Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana.* 18: 151-243. At 176 no.40 fig.14

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